

VR-TALKS

AN ERASMUS+ PROJECT

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Data Collection Instruments

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QUESTIONNAIRE (STUDENTS)

Socio-Demographic Questionnaire

1. What is your age?

- 18-20 years
- 21-25 years
- 26-30 years
- 31-35 years
- 36+ years

2. Gender

- Male
- Female
- Other (*Please specify*): _____
- Prefer not to say

3. Which country are you studying in?

- Czech Republic
- Ireland
- The Netherlands
- Germany
- Portugal
- Other (*Please specify*): _____

4. Are you a:

- Medical student
- Nursing student
- Other (*Please specify*): _____

5. What year are you in?

- First year undergraduate
- Second year undergraduate
- Third year undergraduate
- Fourth year undergraduate
- Fifth year undergraduate
- First year postgraduate
- Second year postgraduate
- Third year postgraduate
- Fourth year postgraduate
- Fifth year postgraduate
- Other (*Please specify*): _____

6. Which virtual reality scenario did you engage with?

- Breaking bad news about patient discharge (Scenario A: Mr. Steward)
- Breaking bad news about cessation of treatment (Scenario B: Mrs. Nora Ibrahim)

7. How much prior experience do you have with virtual reality for leisure (such as gaming)?

- Used once
- Used several times
- Used a lot
- None

8. How much prior experience do you have with virtual reality for educational purposes (such as using virtual reality in your university/studies)?

- Used once
- Used several times
- Used a lot
- None

9. Did you experience any issues as a result of engaging with virtual reality during the current study?

- Yes
- No

10. If your answer to the above question was yes, please indicate what issues you experienced (*Tick as many as apply*):

- Nausea/motion sickness
- Dizziness
- Headache
- Blurred vision
- Eye strain
- Technical issues
- Emotional upset
- Other (*Please specify*): _____

Usability Survey

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements in relation to your experience of engaging with the virtual reality (VR) technology by putting an X in the corresponding box.

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:	Strongly Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Strongly Agree
1. I think I would like to use VR frequently					
2. I found VR unnecessarily complex					
3. I thought VR was easy to use					
4. I think that I would need assistance to be able to use VR					
5. I found the various functions in VR were well integrated					
6. I thought there was too much inconsistency in VR					
7. I would imagine that most people would learn to use VR very quickly					
8. I found VR very cumbersome/awkward to use					
9. I felt very confident using VR					
10. I needed to learn a lot of things before I could get going with VR					

Feasibility Survey

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements in relation to your experience of engaging with the virtual reality (VR) scenario by putting an X in the corresponding box.

Please indicate your level of agreement with the following statements:	Strongly Disagree	Somewhat Disagree	Neither Agree nor Disagree	Somewhat Agree	Strongly Agree
1. Some elements of the VR scenario were confusing					
2. Communication is well represented in the VR scenario					
3. The language used in the VR scenario is appropriate					
4. The instructions within the VR scenario are easy to understand					
5. The font, colour, and size of the written words within the VR scenario are clear					
6. The VR scenario would work with different healthcare professions students					
7. The VR scenario would work with both, undergraduate and postgraduate students					
8. The VR scenario is applicable to real life					
9. The VR scenario can be potentially effective in learning about difficult communication					
10. I learned something valuable from the VR scenario					

Satisfaction Survey

Please indicate your level of satisfaction with the following elements by putting an X in the corresponding box.

Please indicate your level of satisfaction with the following elements:	Extremely Dissatisfied	Dissatisfied	Neither Satisfied nor Dissatisfied	Somewhat Satisfied	Extremely Satisfied
1. Using VR to learn about communication					
2. Overall quality of the VR scenario					

Open-Ended Questions

1. What elements of the VR scenario did you enjoy the most? *(Feel free to write your response in the language you are most comfortable with)*

2. What elements of the VR scenario did you enjoy the least? *(Feel free to write your response in the language you are most comfortable with)*

3. Would you like to see similar VR scenarios used/integrated into your course(s)/programme? If yes, explain how in detail? If no, why not? *(Feel free to write your response in the language you are most comfortable with)*

THANK YOU FOR YOUR PARTICIPATION

QUESTIONNAIRE (EDUCATORS)

Socio-Demographic Questionnaire

1. Gender

- Male
- Female
- Other (*Please specify*): _____
- Prefer not to say

2. How many years have you been teaching for? _____ years

3. What best describes your current position/role?

- Instructor/Tutor/Assistant Lecturer
- Lecturer/Assistant Professor
- Senior Lecturer/Associate Professor
- Professor (Full)
- Other (*Please specify*): _____

4. Which country are you teaching in?

- Czech Republic
- Ireland
- The Netherlands
- Germany
- Portugal
- Other (*Please specify*): _____

5. Are you involved in teaching (*Tick all that apply*):

- Medical students
- Nursing students
- Other (*Please specify*): _____

6. What best describes the programme(s) that you are currently teaching on (*Tick all that apply*)?

- Undergraduate
- Postgraduate

7. Which virtual reality scenario did you engage with?

- Breaking bad news about patient discharge (Scenario A: Mr. Steward)
- Breaking bad news about cessation of treatment (Scenario B: Mrs. Nora Ibrahim)

8. How much prior experience do you have with virtual reality for leisure (such as gaming)?

- Used once
- Used several times
- Used a lot
- None

9. How much prior experience do you have with virtual reality for educational purposes (such as using virtual reality in your courses/programmes/modules)?

- Used once
- Used several times
- Used a lot
- None

10. Did you experience any issues as a result of engaging with virtual reality during the current study?

- Yes
- No

11. If your answer to the above question was yes, please indicate what issues you experienced (*Tick as many as apply*):

- Nausea/motion sickness
- Dizziness
- Headache
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1. Using VR to teach students about communication					
2. Overall quality of the VR scenario					

Open-Ended Questions

1. What elements of the VR scenario did you enjoy the most? *(Feel free to write your response in the language you are most comfortable with):*

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